

TREATMENT OF A NEWBORN WITH CHYLOTHORAX, CHYLOPERICARDIUM AND CHYLOPERITONEUM

Agadjanova Shaira Khalilovna

Scientific supervisor:

Head of the department of pediatrics and neonatology
of the faculty, associate professor, ASMI

Shakhobiddinova Nodirabegim Khabibullo kizi

Independent researcher: ASMI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13933193>

Abstract. The thesis presents a clinical case of successful conservative treatment of a premature newborn with simultaneously developed chylothorax, chylopericardium and chyloperitoneum. The nature of the effusion is confirmed by biochemical studies and the predominance of lymphocytes. Intensive care included long-term parenteral nutrition, octreotide with increasing doses, artificial ventilation and fasting.

Keywords: neonates, chyloperitoneum, chylothorax, intensive care, chylopericardium, octreotide.

INTRODUCTION

Accumulation of lymphatic fluid in the pericardium, pleural or abdominal cavities is a rare disease in the neonatal period with an incidence of 1 case per 15,000 births [1]. Traumatic (iatrogenic), spontaneous and congenital chylous effusion are distinguished. Most often in clinical practice one can see chylothorax and, less often, chyloperitoneum [1, 2]. The occurrence of chylopericardium in newborns, according to literary data, refers to isolated observations [3, 4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Boy Sh. from the 9th pregnancy, which proceeded with the threat of termination in the I-III trimesters, 4 operative deliveries at a gestational age of 30-31 weeks. The mother's medical history includes a genetic form of thrombophilia and chronic arterial hypertension. Assessment on the Apgar scale is 4/6 points, birth weight is 1828 g, length is 42 cm, head circumference is 30 cm, chest circumference is 26 cm. Immediately after birth, the child required artificial ventilation of the lungs (ALV), surfactant was administered endotracheally. In the intensive care unit, artificial ventilation was performed, infusion and antibacterial therapy was prescribed, trophic nutrition was started, a central venous percutaneous catheter was installed through the lower limb. On the 4th day of life, the child's condition worsened: worsening respiratory failure, bronchospasm attacks with cyanosis. X-ray and ultrasound examination (US) revealed right-sided

hydrothorax. The boy was fitted with a pleural drain, which yielded 70 ml of milky fluid. Laboratory tests confirmed the chylous nature of the effusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Octreotide therapy was administered for 20 days with the dose being increased to 10 mcg/kg/h. The child was given a course of intravenous immunoglobulin, repeated transfusions of albumin, red blood cell mass, and fresh frozen plasma (see figure).

At the age of 31 days, the child was extubated, and CPAP respiratory support was administered for 5 days. On the 47th day, enteral feeding with Pregestimil mixture was started with a starting dose of 1 ml/kg/h with gradual expansion. At the age of 2 months 10 days, the boy was discharged home weighing 2640 g.

The etiology and pathogenesis of spontaneous chylous effusion in newborns have not been fully elucidated. A number of literary sources suggest a theory of delayed maturation or hypoplasia of the milk capillaries, the walls of which allow lymph to pass through. The completion of the ontogenesis of the lymphatic system after the birth of the child explains cases of spontaneous recovery during the first months of life [2]. Other sources associate the occurrence of chylothorax with birth trauma, due to damage to the main lymphatic duct and fluid leakage into the pleural cavity [3]. In half of the cases, chylothorax is present immediately after birth, less often it appears during the first week of life. More often, chylothorax, chylopericardium or peritoneum are found in premature babies [3].

The main diagnostic criteria for chylous effusion are laboratory markers: triglycerides >1.1 mmol/l, total cell count >1000 per ml with a predominance of lymphocytes of more than 80% [1]. The predominance of lymphocytes is the most important diagnostic criterion, since in newborns who did not receive enteral nutrition, triglycerides do not increase and the fluid does not have a characteristic milky color. In our observation, all samples contained predominantly lymphocytes, and the fluid from the pleural cavity obtained during the first puncture had a milky color. Due to the small number of observations, there is no generally accepted protocol for the management of newborns with chylous effusion. Therapy for this pathology begins with conservative methods. In the absence of a positive effect within 2-5 weeks, surgical interventions are indicated [4]. First of all, a pleural puncture is performed and/or a pleural drainage is installed to evacuate the fluid, eliminate respiratory distress and conduct diagnostics. Accumulation of chylous fluid in

the pericardial cavity is a life-threatening condition with a high mortality rate, requiring immediate pericardiocentesis. If the chylopericardium persists, a pericardial drainage is installed. To reduce lymph production, a diet with the complete exclusion of fats and enriched with medium-chain triglycerides is indicated, taking into account the peculiarities of lipid metabolism. Absorption of fatty acids in the small intestine depends on the length of the carbohydrate chain. Short- and medium-chain fatty acids are transported by simple diffusion into the intestinal epithelium, bypassing the lymph. Long-chain fatty acids form transport complexes with bile acids. These complexes are called choleic acids. In this form, fatty acids pass through the membrane of the intestinal epithelium with subsequent resynthesis and formation of chylomicrons, which, after absorption through the lymphatic pathways, enter first into the thoracic lymphatic duct and then into the circulatory system.

CONCLUSION

Simultaneous accumulation of chylous effusion in the pericardium, pleural and abdominal cavities is an extremely rare observation in the neonatal period. Treatment of this pathology is a long and complex process; there is no generally accepted protocol. In this observation, conservative therapy, consisting of long-term total parenteral nutrition, cancellation of enteral loading and the use of octreotide, eliminated the lymph leakage and led to a complete recovery of the child.

References:

1. Bellini C., Ergaz Z., Radicioni M., Forner-Cordero I., Witte M., Perotti G., Figar T., Tubaldi L., Camerini P., Bar-Oz B., Yatsiv I., Arad I., Traverso F., Bellini T., Boccardo F., Campisi C., Dalmonte P., Vercellino N., Manikanti S., Bonioli E. Congenital fetal and neonatal visceral chylous effusions: neonatal chylothorax and chylous ascites revisited: A multicenter retrospective study // *Lymphology*. 2012. Vol. 45, N 3. P. 91–102.
2. Downie L., Sasi A., Malhotra A. Congenital chylothorax: associations and neonatal outcomes // *Paediatr. Child Health*. 2014. Vol. 50, N 3. R. 234–238.
3. Nowlen T. T., Rosenthal G. L., Johnson G. L., Tom D. J., Vargo T. A. Pericardial effusion and tamponade in infants with central catheters // *Pediatrics*. 2012. R. 110–137.
4. Rajpal M. N., Buechler L. S., Rao R. Chylous cardiac tamponade due to catheter-associated thrombosis of intrathoracic veins in a newborn infant // *J. Ped. Surg. Case Reports*. 2013. N 1. R. 180–182.